

What does usability testing look like for a participant?

The document is a text only version of a storyboard that demonstrates all the steps a participant will experience when undertaking usability testing. The words and images are described below.

1. Be invited to a usability study

The image shows a person reading a recruitment poster for a research study. They are scanning the poster's QR code with their phone to find out more information.

2. Ask questions

The image shows the person surrounded by lots of question marks flying in different directions all around their head. The researcher stands next to the person, holding a bucket to collect all of the question marks. The researcher is saying, "I can help you with those! You can ask as many questions as you need."

3. Make an informed choice about taking part

The image shows the person with a large thought bubble. The thought bubble includes the following questions:

- Why me?
- Is this research for me?
- What will I be asked to do?
- Will I be comfortable taking part and who do I talk to?
- What are the benefits or drawbacks of taking part?

4. Establish the process for compensation

The image shows the person talking to the researcher about compensation. The researcher says, "Keep your travel receipts so we can reimburse you. We also need to know which voucher you'd like as payment for your time." The person replies, "Thanks. Will there be lunch?"

5. Work out the practicalities

The image shows the person looking at a signpost with four signs and holding a document. Each sign asks one of the following questions:

- What date?
- Where am I going?
- What time?
- Who am I meeting?

6. Give informed consent

The image shows the person holding a consent form and a pen, ready to sign it. There is a thought bubble above the person's head. The text in the thought bubble says, "I know how the research data and my personal data will be collected, stored and used. I know how to access this data. It's okay to withdraw from the study at any time. I'm ready to sign the consent form."

7. Discuss access needs

The image shows the person thinking and writing a list of access needs to discuss with the researcher. The list is an example and it includes the following:

- Will I need specialist equipment?
- Is there a lift?
- I need to change the time.
- I need a screen reader.
- I am bringing someone to support me.

8. Complete the usability tasks

The image shows the person receiving a large box, labelled - usability tasks. The researcher is holding a clipboard and saying, "Remember, ask questions and you can withdraw at any time. We will observe you doing the tasks."

9. Review the research findings

The image shows the person holding an envelope with the results of the research study. Above the person is a thought bubble which says, "The researchers told me how to find the results. I'm going to look and I might give feedback."